

Narrating Essay

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The insulting and endless queue almost made me give up. In my case it was a much desired visit. The magnificent mosaics Hagia Sophia echoed kept inside for a long time in my memory, though I suspect it was more of a must for most of us who were there. Do not believe anyone who dares to visit Istanbul commit sacrilege not to enter one of the icons of the city. And of course, is the long history of this basilica, its name, its protagonists and the city that hosts.

Hagia Sophia, as was known at the time or “Aya Sofya bizantina- Camii” - named for its Turkish conquerors. The basilica has undergone various stages of construction, surviving against all odds, to history: Opened the year 360 by the Emperor Constantine, burned and destroyed in 404, built by Theodosius II again consecrated the year which 415-, 532 succumbs again in flames. The present building owes its existence to the Emperor Justinian, in just five years (532-537), managed to rebuild thanks to arts architect Anthemius of Tralles at that-die a few months after the initiation of reconstruction, and was succeeded by his Isidore of Miletus assistant. Justinian wanted, and apparently got as narrate the ancient sources, turn the basilica in the most magnificent church in Christendom, surpassing the splendor of Solomon in Jerusalem, so did not mind plundering the wealth of other important temples like Diana at Ephesus, the Athens Delphi or Delos and Osiris in Egypt. Marble columns and ornaments were relocated to St. Sophia. The various earthquakes that in the next twenty years there were not destroyed, but damaged the dome tube to be rebuilt. Byzantine Emperors Leo VI and his successors and endowed it with one of its most important decorative elements: mosaic, made from the ninth to twelfth centuries (Maistone, 1988).

All these differences have shaped the unique spirit of this landmark building, which permeates us without conscious-we are just at the very moment we access inside. A single ship,

almost square, supported at its center a magnificent dome about 32 meters in diameter. It consists of 40 nerves that run through masonry, open at the base by small windows that give a false sense of weightlessness. This dome proudly held the title of being the world's largest, until he lost his reign in 1436 when a man named Filippo Brunelleschi came up with an ingenious and innovative system to raise an even larger dome 45 meters in diameter, Florence Duomo. When the city fell under the Turkish Empire, the transformation into a mosque was inevitable. Although the incredible and unusual is that the Turks did not shoot down the most important symbol of Christianity in the East at that time. But again, Hagia Sophia resisted and adapted, becoming Mosque (Macrides & Magdalino, 1988).

I was not able to locate all the Byzantine mosaics that housed St. Sophia, immersed as he was in the chaotic traffic of visitors who eagerly toured the museum. However, I discovered other wonders, like marbles and rich capitals. He needed more time and energy to finish unlocking the secrets of this magnificent building, a great survivor story of men, but had another event. Topkapi Palace waiting for me, and like many other tourists, I could not leave Istanbul committing sacrilege not to visit one of the icons of the city.

References

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